

Survey on Student Proctoring System

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Abstract: *The online Student Proctoring System is designed to provide Rich UI driven components, a user interface for the maintenance of all the records of the student throughout college life. It is used by the universities to maintain the scholastic records of the students easily. The creation and management of accurate, updated information regarding a student's academic career are critically important in the university as well as colleges. The Student information system deals with all kinds of student details, alumni student data, college details, course details, batch details, placement details, and workshop attended other resource-related details too. College students will be able to access his/her portal by logging into his/her account. Staff/student portal is also used to provide information about the college, special events, course details, calendars, academic resources, and contact material*

Keywords: *Component; Interface; Style; Portal*

I. INTRODUCTION

The Student Proctoring System is a web portal where all the information and the services a student needs can be found in one place. Every student of the college will have an account created at the beginning of his Course and it will accessible by the student even after he completes his course. The Stakeholders are Students and Faculty members. It consists of a faculty login along with a student login. In this application all data available such as Alumni student data, Paper Publication data, and Workshop Attended, all data stored on the portal. The impingement of computers in our lives today is probably much more than we are known to.

This Portal is an innovative step towards academic record management as it not only stores the student's academic and scholastic performance, it also generates a computed analysis in the form of graphs and much other visual data which helps the student to reflect upon his/her performance and be motivated to do better. The objective of the Student Proctoring System is to provide an online web-based solution for academic use. In this application all data available such as Alumni student, Paper

Publication, Workshops Attended, Marks Scored, Rank Secured. Easy to use features help our students and staff organize and access information about all aspects of the Alumni student, Paper Publication data, and Workshop Attended in college. Problem Statement : Today's education scenario is rapidly changing and demanding. The system commands greater levels of communication between college, student, and faculty members to have perfect use of resources. Today's industry talent commands are float with more and more skills requirements in all fields. Colleges and institutions generating creative students' needs concerning approach on such talents and industries so as assist best of benefits to their candidates passing out. SPS is a system fulfilling these claims and enacting as a bridge of communication amongst students, faculties, and colleges.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Paper	Proposed System	Gaps
[1]	Survey on implementation of Student Web Portal, providing good infrastructure	Done using outdated technologies like PHP
[2]	The survey focuses on the need for optimal information-based portals that benefit the students	More features apart from the marks list can be added to the portal
[3]	This system was well made with many stakeholders in the consideration	Lacks analysis of data, only stores the marks of the student.
[4]	Provides Multiple different types of user interface to be considers	Not detailed on the methodology used
[5]	In this application, all the features are executed successfully.	The maintenance is done only by an authorized person which is called an admin user. Thus the application is less flexible and changes can be made without

		any difficulty
[6]	The researcher revealed that the student portal management system is good for everyone whatever the organization space or margin, it provides a good sense of organization and management.	The institution should use the system carefully with a closer look into every aspect of its policies and restrictions to every user, which means it should not provide access to each member of the university unless the information solely belongs to them.
[7]	A job web portal provides an efficient search for online information on job vacancies for jobseekers. The main goal of this portal is to attempt to produce the right graduates based on the industry needs	For this Student Portal, the idea may be too overwhelming.
[8]	It uses the latest technologies and it is also user friendly. It has the scope to be expanded in the future. Collect information about various project management techniques which can help to develop the software more efficiently	The project management issues need sorting, In this part, the student considers the project management aspect such as scope, time, and cost which is called a triple constraint in project management to create a successful project.
[9]	Provides Key features that can enhance this project	Irrelevant features to students mentioned in the knowledge Management System.
[10]	web portal which will manage all information regarding colleges. Have decided " Admission Counseling "that will effectively help the student for choosing a college. Eventually, reduce the maximum time requirement of student and providers	Lacks analysis of data, done using outdated old technologies
[11]	Access the files from anywhere Create a backup of your data	Not all application run on cloud Risk related to data protection and security and its integrity
[12]	Institutions of higher learning can allow their technological	Security and Privacy Real Benefits: Service Quality: Lack of adequate

infrastructure to be used by other firms as a way of enhancing research. 2The efficiency associated	network responsiveness: Integration:
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Table 1. Survey table

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

Our group will be creating a new Portal overpowering the old decade portal by using the latest technologies that are being used today. Earlier it was done in PHP, but as they are outdated we have decided to use ReactJS, NodeJS, MongoDB, and many other various tools.

The objective of the STUDENT PROCTORING SYSTEM is to provide an online web-based solution for academic use. In this application, all data will be available such as Alumni student, Marks Secured, Class Rank, Forums, Placement Officer Functionalities Paper Publication data, and all other Achievements. Every student and staff will provide a unique login id and password. Also, all the data will be at least once validated from the college database. For this purpose, the college database is being retrieved directly. So, this process also helps in maintaining consistency and integrity. The student and staff acquaintance system that helps users can readily store the students and staff's information online. The user can readily store and retrieve the data department wise online. This system helps the user to generate dynamic legwork. So the user can conveniently interact with the system to readily and access the resources.

IV. CONCLUSION

From the above Survey, it can be said that the relation between the education sector and the field of data analytics and cloud computing will be an important combination that should not be overlooked.

We know that the computer has changed the course of human interaction. This paper describes a face in reality and the other step is to identify the object.

This application will help the stakeholders like the students and the teachers to maintain, analyze the various information that will be stored in this system. The goal has always been to provide a UI rich interface with extremely useful tools the student can make use of.

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